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Наименование материала: «THE IMPORTANCE OF FOLK CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL CULTURE»

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Abstract

This article discusses how the concept of independence is linked to national values, and that the independence of the state plays a key role in the revival of values.

Keywords: value, tradition, independence, ritual, spirituality, enlightenment, phenomenon, national values, ideology, revival.

INTRADUCTION

Today our country has passed the way from the national revival to the national progress. Changes and reforms happening in the society of Uzbekistan, in its social political, economical and spiritual enlightenment spheres more and more are raising people's belief to the future. Due to the facts that our motherland is entering bravely world's commonwealth society and turning into an open state make widen the line of people admitting the achievements gained by the people of our country. All these are the phenomenon, the value which our people have been dreamed for many centuries – all these happened thanks to the Independence. The concept of the word “mustaqillik”, originated from the Arabian, means disobedience to others, that the nation and country themselves can manage and they themselves realize their persisting goals and objectives without being subordinate. Within many centuries three thousand-year-old history of the Uzbek nation had to suffer colonial torment and faced lots of losses.

For the last twenty nine years our country with its nation has had their own word in the global community, and now other countries in the international tribunes are consulting with our decision to solve global problems, our views have begun to be considered. Not long ago we needed someone's advice in the questions connected with political system, politics, economy, spirituality, ideology even in minor issues, now

we have the opportunity to solve all this on the basis of the wishes and steadfastness of our people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Undeniably, the Independence is considered our people's great value. At the same time this phenomenon created wide possibility to the development of national values, traditions and customs, revival of traditions, which were soaked deeply into the blood of the Uzbek people. The attention paid to our values and the efforts exerted on their revival and development is very dear for us. The fact is that, during the period of the former system of Soviet Union the ideology of that time tried to weaken our national values in any ways, there were attempts to saturate alien ideology, that were not appropriate to our good and instead of our national values they did any kind of dreamed up an ideology to insult the nation.

At present it is pleasant to say that we are very grateful for a particular attention that is paid to a revival of our national values and to increase the place of before trampled values in our national development. A lot has already been done on this subject. The tasks, like reviving the nation's national values, formation of moral ideals and increasing intellectual ability are involved as the most important aim in the Action Strategy on the direction of five updated development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years of 2017-2021.

It should be marked separately, the tasks set by the president on modernization of the state and society require a serious investigation of thoughts and views on real comprehending and studying widely the system of values that have priority among the population; it is also necessary to know the factors of citizen's attitude, particularly the young generation's, towards the national values. In its turn they undoubtedly help to determine spiritual sources not only in the development of the society, but as well as to define at what level they correspond to socio- cultural modernization and transformation of values which are traditional to Uzbekistan. In the recent years in our country lots of work has been done to reconstruct our national values, to improve them correspondingly to the positive changes happening in our society. It is very important here to emphasize the Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan (dated

from November 28, 2018) “On approval of the concept for further development of the national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”. The present document pays particular attention to infiltrate our national and universal values into the consciousness of our youth, protect ethnic cultural traditions and on the basis of this to support people’s folk art, to educate citizens and especially, the young generation in the spirit of national values[P.1].

And there is a question: what is the concept of “value”, what definition can be given to it? It should be said there is not any the only, concrete definition of the term. But many people believe that the word “qadriyat” (“value”) having the meaning of quantity, expensive things, treasure of the nation in the Arabian language, is used to denote human values, social-moral, cultural - spiritual significance of definite events in real life.

The things that are very dear to a human and humanity, like freedom, peace, equality, enlightenment, truth, kindness, beauty, material and spiritual wealth, traditions, customs and habits are Values. The category of values is used not only to express economical quality of things and objects, but they are also used to mean the value of forms, states, things, events, happenings, requirements and procedure of the reality and others that have importance for a human and the society.

There is one more thing that needs to be pointed, because of the influence of social processes people’s imaginations and opinions on values can be systematically transformed. Due to the historical needs one or the other value steps forward social progress. For example, when enemy conquers a country there is Liberty; at the end of the reign of the empire – Independence; within the war – Peace; being in prison – Freedom; during the sickness and ill health – health, thus the value of these becomes stronger [P.2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is known, that values can be universal, national or personal. The values that express the most important features, law and regulations of the universe, nature and society

have universal peculiarities. This type of values never loses their importance and value, their worth always increases. The values that are associated with a definite nation, country, people's life, their life style, language, culture spirituality, habits and customs, traditions, past time, and future are considered national values. And personal values are the values connected with a human, his activity, life style, religion, meaning of life and his behavior.

Now, let's look through what peculiarities can be included to the system of above mentioned values. The system of universal values involves the values as, peace, mutual cooperation, respect for the value of other nations, solidarity, protection of the environment, and the most important ones – democratic values. In the system of the national values the following features, like patriotism, respect to the mother tongue, sense of national pride, respect for his historical heritage, peace ability, devotion to the national traditions, respect for the national habits and customs, patience, tolerance, credulity, careful attitude towards the family values, respect elderly people, hospitality, generosity have an important place.

Within the years of the Independence there have been done certain tasks to reconstruct our national values, to increase their role in our national development. Moreover, we must not forget that past years have been the years of enriching our national values with the new qualities. In particular, our country is moving into an open society in strict sense, the market economy widely carrying out in the country, various positive and negative events entering our country due to the global processes – all these form certain changes in the system of our national values.

Frankly speaking, national values are considered as an important factor that brings up a human's noble and positive qualities and superiorities. In this sense we all should admit that the national values are an emergency phenomenon arising good and soul-saving qualities of our national values. That is, a national value is a protecting means that defends us from different negative directions and bad habits challenging us to be perfectly educated people. Most respectable and fruitful historian, writer and poet Ghiyosiddin Khondamir (1475-1535) in his book "Makorimul-akhloq" ("Noble behavior") noted that the value of every person is determined by his or her beautiful

properties. "The people owning keen mind whose point of view decorates the world and those with sensitivity and great intellect, which helps make it easier their difficulties must be aware of the fact",-said Khondamir, -" if God wants someone to be good, God rewards him with good behavior". According to his opinion, due to the will of God, the creator with special powers in creating everything he wanted and the one who has not got any similarities, if he wants someone to achieve material and spiritual happiness or religious and earthly wealth God dresses up that person with attractive appearance and beautiful looks, as Almighty would like to have in his habitation only the ones with the positive intellectual mind liberated and freed from all vile intentions and bad jerks"(GhiyosiddinKhondamir."Makorimul-akhloq".[3.P.288].

In fact, the above mentioned pretty long definition is a manual that can show a human's dignity and value in strict sense. It is spoken there about a man's keen intellect, consciousness, good and beautiful behavior, awareness, positive peculiarities, spiritually good looking face, attractive soul –and all these make our national values.

In some place above we have stated the fact that at today's step of our social development some values may have priority than the others. Indeed, that is true. In our opinion, at present we can see the cases that were not worth attention before – it is becoming commonplace to help socially disadvantaged people paying them special attention. This case shows the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan what generous humane policy he is pursuing – taking care of orphans, patronize them providing with housing. The most important thing is that today showing generosity, beneficence and donation is forming as one of the most necessary values.

KhusainVoisKoshifiy (1442-1505), a famous scholar of the East, expounded that generous donation and benefitting the population meant doing the right thing. Being generous is a positive reason of being familiar to everyone. And donating to the population is a good cause of showing your love to them. No quality, property and dignity of are better than showing generosity by the rich and affluent. One need to know well, if a person does not spend his fortune for other people, they will not achieve the title of greatness and sense of delight. In order to obtain earthy bliss, it is necessary

to please the souls of people with their good deeds. As the soul is the king of the body, if it is hunted by someone the body being obedient to the soul, there is no other way then to obey the soul. In accordance with this concept if someone contribute people's souls with his denotation the doors of the happiness will open for him and thus he will achieve his dreams (KhuseinVoisKoshifiy. Futuvvatnomaisultoniyy. Akhlokiymukhsiniy.[4. P.198]).

Today the measurements holding in our country, like helping the needy, raising their souls are considered the most important sights of our national values and numbers of such phenomena are getting more and more. This shows the formation of a healthy environment in the society. Many such examples can be given.

It is well known, that the Uzbek people since ancient times have been accustomed to hold any kind of measurement that belong to our national values together, in consultation with each other. Particularly, weddings, funerals and these kind of other activities have always been held in harmony with all relatives, neighbours and friends. Surely, from one hand there are a lot of many positive sides, from the other hand, in some cases, under the pretext of a wedding, some try to show their wealth in an attempt to surpass one another. We must not forget that this may cause discontent in the public.

Wedding ceremonies are one of the great values of the Uzbek people. We think those people to win fake authority or false respect are poisoning our values, which negatively influences to the ancient traditions. Excess wedding expenses, display one's wealth, undoubtedly, lead in education of the young people the appearance of other deeds. Right here, we consider it is necessary to quote Sheikh Muhammad Yusuf's opinions: a Muslim should be moderate when spending money or fortune. He must not waste excessively and pointlessly his wealth and at the same time he should not be excessively stingy, he should not refuse to spend the right amount in the right place. [5. P.148].

Indeed, as the great Sheikh emphasized wasting one's wealth for nothing, for shed activities means not understanding the meaning of the word 'squandering', actually it is one of the sights of sinful nature. Nowadays if someone thinks, like

“It is my fortune, is not it? I spend as I think is right”. That is not true, of course. The movement of helping for orphans and socially needy people is increasing in the society year by year. In particular, our citizens, elderly fathers and mothers who are preparing to the hajj (a journey to the holy city of Mecca that Muslims make as a religious duty), before they visit socially needy people and families in their makhallas, in the villages supporting them materially and spiritually. This is an example of our values being enriched by new trends.

In essence, man himself is the highest value. The great thinker DjaloliddinRumiy, (1207-1273), claimed many times that man is the highest majesty. Addressing man he emphasized that man is just great miracle, everything is written inside him, therefore he must not sell himself as a cheap substance, because its cost is very high.[6. P.119].

And in truth, in the years of our Independence, particularly in last three- four years the essence of the man is being revealed in the literal sense. In particular, the factors like, “The benefit of mankind is above all”, “People should not serve the organs of the government, but the organs of the government must serve the people”, “If the people are rich, the government is also rich and powerful”, “Justice is the priority of laws”, “Where there is no spirituality there is no justice” inform that man is the most treasured value in the world.

There is one more thing that should be paid attention. The world is developing at an accelerating pace today, in all spheres it is going through processes of powerful integration. Globalization is showing positive and negative influences. It is in such conditions, the change of values, or in other words, transformation processes take place. Only yesterday the values we admired were proud today we feel awkward with shame. Some cases that were out of our focus today they turned into national values.

For instance, such aspirations as becoming a lively, businesslike, wealthy person, choosing a specific goal and striving for it, desiring to become a citizen of a state that obeys all state laws, gaining knowledge that will make it vital in life become valuable for our youth. But at the same time, there are such cases when a tendency

toward redundancy develops in our society, which turns them into owners. And one does not want to close eyes.[7. P. 320].

CONCLUSION

- The philosopher A. Erkaev pointed out, that for a person striving to the richness, treasure and wealth –all these is the head of any value; in his opinion these values take the highest place in the hierarchy of values. And there is someone who is careerist. In order to get high position he is ready to do any kind of meanness. Reaching well-paid high position for him is the highest place in the hierarchy of values. The people striving for wealth and career are very dangerous for the society, in the result of which bribery and corruption will spread along the society. Certainly, preliminary calculation of most people's value is positive. And our aim is to enrich these positive values with new qualities which can reply to the requirement of today's demands.
- Today we can see that the process in which many values now are becoming priceless. Such processes in the history of mankind were even the causes of the fall of society, empire. The transformation of values into priceless occurs as a result of national benefits, distrust of state policy, disappointment of the people from some phenomenon, and increased distrust. This kind of cases can be seen in many countries. Beside the exclusion of certain values, blowing them all does not lead to positive results.
- According to the right policy of our president and right comprehension of these questions by the members of our society we have chosen moderate way in the issues regarding to the values and this fully matches the benefits of our citizens. Our national values serve as an important source in the education of our young generation; they are carrying out the foundation tasks in the transition from national revival to national progress. The development of the society depends on values that will become our belief. Such values strengthen the national community, ensure intergenerational inheritance.

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